

THE INFLUENCE OF CUSTOMER VALUES ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND ITS IMPACT ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY WITH THE MODERATION EFFECT OF CAFE ATMOSPHERE IN LHOKSEUMAWE CITY

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine the influence of customer value on customer satisfaction and its impact on customer loyalty with the moderating effect of cafe atmosphere in Lhokseumawe City. The data in this study were 120 employees who responded to a questionnaire distributed through Google Form. The data analysis tool used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) operated with Amos. The results of the study found that customer value significantly influenced job satisfaction and customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction also significantly increased customer loyalty. And in testing the mediation effect of customer satisfaction significantly mediated the influence of customer value on customer loyalty. Furthermore, in testing the moderation effect, cafe atmosphere significantly moderated the influence of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty. The results of this study are expected to provide important contributions for stakeholders in developing cafe business marketing strategies in the future.

Keywords: *customer value, customer satisfaction, cafe atmosphere, customer loyalty.*

INTRODUCTION

The food and beverage (F&B) industry in Indonesia continues to show positive and sustainable growth. Although impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic, this sector quickly recovered and once again became a major contributor to the non-oil and gas Gross Domestic Product (GDP), according to data from the Ministry of Industry. In 2023, the F&B sector recorded stable growth with increased domestic and international investment, in line with the large potential of the Indonesian market, which has a population of more than 270 million. In Lhokseumawe City, the cafe industry is experiencing dynamic development. Many new cafes have emerged with diverse concepts that attract young people and professionals. However, many have closed due to a failure to retain customers. This shows that a cafe's success is determined not only by location or design, but also by its ability to create value for customers. In the culinary industry, this value is influenced by design, ambiance, taste, portion size, healthy food options, convenience, price, and menu availability (Hasan, 2022).

Considering the dynamics of the cafe business in Lhokseumawe City, as well as the importance of understanding customer value, satisfaction, loyalty, and the influence of cafe atmosphere, this research is relevant. The results of this study are expected to provide a real contribution to cafe business actors in formulating effective strategies to maintain and increase their customer loyalty. A business aims to gain a competitive advantage by creating good customer value. The characteristics that influence customer loyalty are explored in this study because they provide benefits to the company. Customer loyalty is a benchmark used to make a business successful, especially in the service industry, particularly in the culinary sector. Customer loyalty is a crucial aspect that needs to be created by every company, where loyal customers are the key to long-term business success. Customer loyalty is an important factor because it is not easy for companies to get new customers than to retain loyal customers who do not easily switch to using other services (Ashraf, Ilyas, Imtiaz, and Ahmad, 2018). Value, Satisfaction, and Loyalty are important topics in tourism and hospitality research including restaurants and cafes (Gallarza-granizo, Ruiz-molina, and Schlosser, 2019). Concepts such as customer value and customer loyalty have been extensively researched and are considered fundamental to industries that rely on repeat customers and positive word-of-mouth. In addition to customer retention, another factor every company needs to improve is customers' positive perception of value (customer value), where value is considered a key factor in creating customer loyalty. In achieving

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sustainable competitive advantage, Tankovic & Benazic, (2018) He stated that value is a crucial point in marketing, because the value provided to customers can be a benchmark for a company's success. Although decades of research have explored the concept of customer value, a consistent theoretical and conceptual understanding of the concept has yet to be achieved comprehensively (Haghkhah and Asgari, 2000). Although the concept of customer value is relativistic, research on differences in perception of Value across cultures is still rare (Gallarza-granizo et al., 2019). According to Sendawula et al., (2019), Modern businesses must be oriented towards customer satisfaction because perceived satisfaction is the starting point for increasing loyalty and competitive advantage for the company. Harzaviona & Syah, (2020), Satisfied customers are a benefit to a company because they are less likely to switch to other brands or products. Previous studies have also validated the role of customer satisfaction as a mediator between perceived customer value and customer loyalty (Chikazhe, Makanyeza, and Chigunhah, 2021; Gong and Yi, 2021).

In addition to value and satisfaction, cafe customer loyalty is also influenced by the cafe's atmosphere. Cafe atmosphere encompasses elements such as interior and exterior design, lighting, aroma and temperature, music, and service (Risal, Efendi, and Firmanzah, 2025). A well-created atmosphere can create comfort and create a pleasant emotional experience for customers, which ultimately influences customer satisfaction and even loyalty (Atsnawiyah, Mohamad Rizan, and Rahmi, 2021). With increasing consumer expectations for a holistic experience in cafes, atmosphere management is becoming a strategic factor that cannot be ignored. However, the relationship between atmosphere, satisfaction, and customer loyalty remains controversial in various studies. Some studies suggest that atmosphere directly influences customer loyalty (Hikmah, Sriyanti, Payangan, and Mustafa, 2023; Mudjiyanti, 2022), while other studies found that the influence was indirect through customer satisfaction as a mediator and atmosphere as a moderator (Nyoman, Cakra, Hidayat, and Lestariningsih, 2021). Furthermore, most previous studies were conducted with limited generalizability within a geographic context or were conducted locally and limited to a specific region. Therefore, the results cannot be easily generalized to other regions, which may have different cultural characteristics and customer lifestyles. Based on the background, phenomena and gaps, this research has a strategic position in filling the existing scientific vacuum, namely by positioning the cafe atmosphere variable as a moderating variable between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty, which in the end this research is expected to provide a significant theoretical contribution in the development of science, as well as having strategic relevance in helping the development of the cafe industry in building customer retention effectively, especially in the cafe business in the Lhokseumawe City area.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Perception of Customer Value and Customer Satisfaction

Customer value is an interactive experience and it is an additional component of customer value (Gallarza, 2022). According to, Im & Qu, (2021), Customer value is the values that customers receive and evaluate that depend on the features of a product or service, value cannot occur without the involvement or interaction of customers who value these features which is very important for the restaurant industry which is a people-oriented industry. Customer perceived value is a trade-off between the benefits of the offer and the sacrifices felt by the customer (Blut, Chaney, and Lunardo, 2024; Tankovic and Benazic, 2018; Widjaja and Araufi, 2020). In previous studies, Rahman, (2018) stated that customer-perceived value significantly influences increasing restaurant customer satisfaction. Furthermore, perceived value was also found to significantly influence customer satisfaction (Patil and Rane, 2023; Qiu, Li, Pan, Wu, and Guo, 2024; Saputra, 2018), including emotional values (Rafdinal and Suhartanto, 2020). The study of the concept of value is seen as increasingly important amidst increasingly fierce competition in the cafe industry. Even in many developed countries, value remains a crucial benchmark for increasing customer satisfaction (Guhl, Blankart, and Stargardt, 2019), although in some other parts it is considered not to affect cafe customer satisfaction (El-Adly, 2019), Two dimensions of perceived value in the hospitality context, namely aesthetics and prestige, were found to have no significant direct influence on customer satisfaction or customer loyalty. Based on the opinions of previous researchers, the hypothesis statement is:

H₁: Customer value has a significant influence on customer satisfaction in cafes in Lhokseumawe City.

Customer Value and Customer Loyalty

Value is a topic that has been applied widely and deeply in restaurant and hospitality services within the scope of customer experience (Bueno, Weber, Bomfim, and Kato, 2019). Furthermore, Guhl et al., (2019), concluded that there is a strong positive interdependence between perceived value and customer satisfaction. Increasing customer value will have an impact on increasing customer loyalty (Gallarza-granizo et al., 2019). Customer perceived value is the customer's view of the value they receive for the money they spend compared to other options

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(Gabriella Santoso and Ruslim, 2024). Researchers concluded that perceived value is a customer's overall assessment of the benefits or value derived from a product or service relative to the costs incurred. This suggests that perceived value can increase customer satisfaction and loyalty (Jeong and Kim, 2019). Then the study, Gabriella Santoso & Ruslim, (2024) found that customer value has a significant influence on customer loyalty. Based on the opinions of previous researchers, the hypothesis developed is:

H₂: Customer value has a significant influence on customer loyalty in cafes in Lhokseumawe City.

Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty

Customer satisfaction was found to have a direct positive effect on customer loyalty (El-Adly, 2019). Furthermore, Guhl et al., (2019), found a strong positive interdependence between perceived customer value and customer satisfaction. In a study of several restaurants in Tangerang City (Karani, Syah, and Anindita, 2019) found a significant influence between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. In several studies in the food and beverage industry in more developed countries, customer satisfaction is believed to be an important factor in increasing customer loyalty (Leroi-Werelds, 2019). Gopi & Samat, (2020) said customer satisfaction has a significant influence on customer loyalty. Tourist satisfaction has a significant influence on subsequent visits (Gabriella Santoso and Ruslim, 2024; Jeong and Kim, 2019). Based on the opinions of previous researchers, the hypothesis developed is:

H₃: Customer satisfaction has a significant influence on customer loyalty in cafes in Lhokseumawe City.

Cafe Atmosphere and Customer Loyalty

The cafe industry has seen rapid growth in recent years, particularly in large cities and urban areas, where cafes are no longer just places to eat and drink, but also social spaces, co-working spaces, and lifestyle outlets. Increasing competition requires cafe owners to focus not only on the quality of their food and beverage products but also on creating an atmosphere that creates a holistic experience for customers. According to, Kotler (1973) in Kotler & Armstrong, Gary, (2018), Atmosphere is the result of consciously designing a space to create a specific psychological effect on customers. In the context of a cafe, atmosphere encompasses interior design, lighting, aroma, background music, temperature, cleanliness, and even the interaction between staff and customers. All of these elements indirectly shape visitors' perceptions and comfort, influencing satisfaction and even the decision to return. Recent studies have shown that atmosphere has a significant influence on consumer behavior. Studies by Rafli et al., (2024) at Meraki Café, Cirebon, and several other researchers, such as (Atsnawiyah et al., 2021; Mudjiyanti, 2022; Risal et al., 2025), shows that the cafe atmosphere can influence customer satisfaction and loyalty. A similar finding was also found by (Hidayati, Agus, and Zamzam, 2024; Hikmah et al., 2023), which states that store atmosphere has a strong impact on consumers' decisions to revisit. This shows that atmosphere is not just an aesthetic element, but a strategic part of efforts to build long-term relationships with customers. This study was conducted to further examine the influence of cafe atmosphere on customer loyalty, by considering various dimensions of atmosphere such as interior design, lighting, aroma, music, temperature, cleanliness, and social interaction. By understanding this relationship, it is hoped that cafe business owners can design more appropriate strategies to retain customers and increase competitiveness in an increasingly competitive market. Based on the opinions of previous researchers, the developed hypothesis is:

H₄: Cafe atmosphere has a significant influence on cafe customer loyalty in Lhokseumawe City.

Customer Value and Customer Loyalty through Customer Satisfaction as a Mediating Variable

Customer perceived value of hotel services has a significant indirect positive influence on customer loyalty, with customer satisfaction acting as a mediator (El-Adly, 2019; Guhl et al., 2019). Then according to, Cho et al., (2020) He stated that customer satisfaction is important for encouraging customer loyalty, which is previously derived from perceived value. Then, a study in the public sector found that customer satisfaction can mediate the relationship between perceived value and customer loyalty (Gabriella Santoso and Ruslim, 2024; Jeong and Kim, 2019). Based on the opinions of previous researchers, the hypothesis developed is:

H₅: Customer value has a significant influence on cafe customer loyalty in Lhokseumawe City with customer satisfaction as a mediating variable.

The Moderating Role of Cafe Atmosphere in the Influence of Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty

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Customer satisfaction has long been considered a key factor influencing customer loyalty. When customers are satisfied with their experience, they are more likely to return, recommend, and build long-term relationships with that brand or location (Atsnawiyah et al., 2021). However, in the context of cafes, the relationship between satisfaction and loyalty is not always direct or linear. One variable that has the potential to moderate (strengthen or weaken) this relationship is the cafe's atmosphere. According to, Risal et al., (2025), A cafe's atmosphere can strengthen the influence of satisfaction on customer loyalty in several ways. First, it increases emotional closeness. This means that a comfortable, attractive, and pleasant atmosphere makes customers feel more connected to the cafe. As a result, the satisfaction they feel can turn into a desire to keep coming back. Second, it creates a holistic experience. This occurs when customers are satisfied with the food and service, supported by a supportive atmosphere such as pleasant music, fragrant aromas, and appropriate lighting, then they will consider the cafe a suitable and pleasant place to visit again. And third, it reduces disappointment. Where in certain situations, for example when the service is not very satisfactory, a cafe atmosphere that remains positive can help reduce customer disappointment and make them want to return again another time. Several previous studies found cafe atmosphere as a moderating variable in the relationship between customer satisfaction and cafe customer loyalty, such as (Atsnawiyah et al., 2021), and yet the study Benamen et al., (2024), found different results, namely that the cafe atmosphere did not moderate the influence of satisfaction on loyalty. Based on the opinions of previous researchers, the following hypothesis was developed:

H₆: Cafe Atmosphere Moderates the Influence of Customer Satisfaction on Cafe Customer Loyalty in Lhokseumawe City.

Furthermore, to analyze the balance of the research model used, this study includes customer satisfaction variables as mediation and cafe atmosphere as a control variable (Chi and Phan, 2025; Ma, QU, and Eliwa, 2020; Rachmawati and Nugroho, 2021). Based on the description of the empirical study, the research model is as follows:

Figure 1 Research Conceptual Framework

METHOD

Data and Sampling Techniques

The data used in this study were primary data collected through a questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed via Google Forms to sample cafe visitors. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling, with a sample size of 120 people.

Data Analysis Method

The data analysis method used in this study was Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using the AMOS (Analysis of Moment Structure) program version 22.0. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is a multivariate analysis technique that combines factor analysis and regression (correlation) analysis. It aims to examine the relationships between variables in a model, both between indicators and their constructs, and the relationships between constructs (Ghozali, 2013). SEM combines two statistical concepts: factor analysis, which is included in the measurement model, and regression, using a structural model.

Operational Definition of Variables

This study involved four latent variables, each measured by several indicators or statement items adopted from previous studies. The questionnaire statement items are shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1 Operational Definition of Variables

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Variables	Operational Definition of Variables	Code	Indicator
Perceived Customer Value	Customer Value Perception is the perception or level of customer satisfaction regarding the benefits received while using products and services and compared to the sacrifices (costs) made by the customer.	CV1	1. In my opinion, the food and beverage products in this cafe are of good quality.
		CV2	2. In my opinion, the service process at this cafe is fast and efficient.
		CV3	3. In my opinion, the service staff showed a polite and professional attitude.
		CV4	4. In my opinion, the price of this product/service is commensurate with the benefits I get.
		CV5	5. In my opinion, I don't need to spend much time to get this product/service. Source: Soliha et al., (2021)
Customer Satisfaction	Customer Satisfaction is the level of cognitive and emotional satisfaction that customers feel after using a product, brand or service.	CS1	1. I was satisfied with my experience at this cafe.
		CS2	2. I enjoyed the time I spent at this cafe.
		CS3	3. Visiting this cafe is a wise decision.
		CS4	4. The quality of food and service at this cafe met my expectations.
		CS5	5. Overall, I am satisfied with this cafe. Source: Dhisasmito & Kumar, (2020)
Café Atmosphere	Cafe atmosphere is a complex combination of physical and non-physical environment that greatly influences customer satisfaction, return intention and loyalty.	AC1	1. The room temperature in this cafe feels comfortable for me.
		AC2	2. The air circulation inside this cafe feels good and refreshing.
		AC3	3. The noise level in this cafe does not disturb my comfort.
		AC4	4. The music played in this cafe adds to the comfortable atmosphere.
		AC5	5. The aroma inside this cafe is pleasant and not disturbing. Source: Benamen et al., (2024)
Customer Loyalty	Customer Loyalty is a customer's commitment to repurchase or use products and services consistently, even when there is a temptation to use alternative or competing products.	CL1	1. I often say positive things about this cafe to others.
		CL2	2. I would recommend this cafe to anyone who asks for advice.
		CL3	3. Encourage friends and relatives to do business with this coffee shop.
		CL4	4. I intend to visit this cafe again in the future.
		CL5	5. I will still shop at this cafe even if the prices increase. Source: Dhisasmito & Kumar, (2020)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Result

The respondents in this study were 115 cafe visitors. The following will systematically explain the description of the respondent profiles used in this study, such as gender, age, education, marital status, occupation, and income. Respondent characteristics are described as follows:

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Table 2 Respondent Characteristics

Respondent Characteristics		Amount	%
Gender	Male	77	67
	Female	38	33
	Total	115	100
Age	< 20 Years	19	17
	20-30 Years	30	26
	30-40 Years	34	30
	40-50 Years	24	21
	> 50 Years	8	7
	Total	115	100
Educational level	Junior High School/Equivalent	4	3
	High School/Equivalent	22	19
	Diploma	29	25
	Bachelor's Degree	51	44
	Postgraduate	9	8
	Total	115	100
Marital status	Marry	86	75
	Not Married	29	25
	Total	115	100
Type of work	Self-employed	32	28
	Private employees (BUMD/BUMN)	25	22
	Government employees (ASN/TNI/Polri)	17	15
	Housewife	13	11
	Students	28	24
	Total	115	100
Income	< 3 Million	17	15
	3-6 Million	41	36
	6-9 Million	35	30
	> 9 Million	22	19
	Total	115	100

Based on Table 2 above, it can be explained that the respondents in this study were predominantly male, namely 67%. The majority were aged between 20 and 40 years, reaching 56%. The highest education level was a bachelor's degree (44%). Furthermore, the study found that 75% of respondents were married. From an occupational perspective, 57% of cafe visitors were self-employed or private employees, with the highest income ranging from 3 to 9 million rupiah.

Data Validity and Reliability Test Results

The construct validity testing model in this study used Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) is conducted by comparing the loading factor values for each variable. According to Ghozali (2014), an indicator is considered valid if its loading factor value is greater than 0.60. Construct validity testing in this study was conducted partially for each exogenous and endogenous variable. The results of the CFA analysis for all variables are explained below:

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Table 3 Validity Test Results

Statement Items		Loading Factor Value	Cut Off Value	Conclusion
NP1	<--- Customer Value	0,651	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
NP2	<--- Customer Value	0,712	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
NP3	<--- Customer Value	0,72	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
NP4	<--- Customer Value	0,814	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
NP5	<--- Customer Value	0,712	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
KP1	<--- Customer satisfaction	0,78	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
KP2	<--- Customer satisfaction	0,778	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
KP3	<--- Customer satisfaction	0,703	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
KP4	<--- Customer satisfaction	0,689	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
AC1	<--- Cafe Atmosphere	0,807	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
AC2	<--- Cafe Atmosphere	0,7	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
AC3	<--- Cafe Atmosphere	0,751	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
AC4	<--- Cafe Atmosphere	0,723	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
LP1	<--- Customer Loyalty	0,718	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
LP2	<--- Customer Loyalty	0,653	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
LP3	<--- Customer Loyalty	0,763	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
LP4	<--- Customer Loyalty	0,751	$\geq 0,60$	Valid
LP5	<--- Customer Loyalty	0,752	$\geq 0,60$	Valid

Table 3 shows that the statement items for all latent variables have loading factor values greater than 0.60. Based on these data, it can be concluded that all statement items have met the requirements of the CFA model (Ghozali, 2014). Therefore, it can be concluded that the data used is statistically valid. Furthermore, to assess whether the statement items have met the data reliability criteria, this is shown in Table 4 below:

Table 4 Results of Data Reliability Test

Variables	Construct Reliability		Variance Extracted	
	Acquisition Value	Cut Off Value	Acquisition Value	Cut Off Value
Customer Value	0,927	$\geq 0,7$	0,537	$\geq 0,5$
Customer satisfaction	0,827	$\geq 0,7$	0,546	$\geq 0,5$
Cafe Atmosphere	0,834	$\geq 0,7$	0,557	$\geq 0,5$
Customer Loyalty	0,847	$\geq 0,7$	0,526	$\geq 0,5$

Based on the data shown in Table 4, it can be explained that the variables of customer value, customer satisfaction, cafe atmosphere and customer loyalty have CR values that are much greater than 0.70, and thus it can be concluded that these variables have very good reliability values. The Variance Extracted (VE) values obtained by the variables of customer value, customer satisfaction, cafe atmosphere and customer loyalty are also much greater than the required 0.50, thus it can be concluded that the variables of customer value, customer satisfaction, cafe atmosphere and customer loyalty have good convergent values (sharing a high proportion of variance).

Research Hypothesis Testing Results

To determine the extent to which the initial model developed in this study meets the Goodness of Fit (GOF) criteria, a test was conducted on the entire model for structural model 1, which involved all variables. The results of the overall test of the research path model are shown in Figure 2 below:

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Figure 2 Structural Model 1

Figure 2 above shows that structural model 1, after undergoing the index modification process, has met the goodness of fit test criteria. This means the data is appropriate and can explain the model well. This structural model has good scores for eight GoF criteria, and overall, the model is acceptable because it meets all the required criteria and has good scores. For more clarity, see Table 5 below:

Table 5 Goodness of Fit Model

No.	Criteria	Expected Value	Yield Value	Conclusion
1	Chi Square	Expected to be small	89.071	Good
2	Goodness of fit Index (GFI)	> 0.90	0.910	Good
3	Adjusted Goodness Ft of Index (AGFI)	> 0.90	0.867	Good
4	Tucker Lewis Index (TLI)	> 0.95	0.967	Good
5	Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	> 0.95	0.974	Good
6	Root Mean Square error of Approximation (RMSEA)	< 0.08	0.046	Good
7	CMIND/DF	< 2.00	1.255	Good
8	P-Value	> 0.05	0.072	Good

Then, the regression weight value for the direct influence of customer value on customer satisfaction can be shown in Table 6 below:

Table 6 Direct Effects

			Std. Estimate	Unstd. Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Customer satisfaction	<---	Customer Value	0,223	0,257	0,125	2,046	0.041
Customer Loyalty	<---	Customer Value	0,608	0,556	0,101	5,488	0.000
Customer Loyalty	<---	Customer satisfaction	0,321	0,255	0,072	3,554	0.000

Based on Table 6, it can be explained that the regression weight value of the influence of customer value on customer satisfaction is 0.223 and a significance value of 0.041 (≤ 0.05). Then the regression weight of the influence of customer value on customer loyalty is 0.608, with a significance value of 0.000 (≤ 0.05). Furthermore, the regression weight value of the influence of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty is 0.321, with a significance value of 0.000 (≤ 0.05). This shows that customer value has a significant effect on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. Likewise, the influence of customer satisfaction was found to influence customer loyalty in cafes in Lhokseumawe City.

The Influence of Mediation Effect

A mediation effect analysis was conducted to determine whether customer satisfaction variables can mediate the influence of customer value on customer loyalty. The mediation effect test was conducted by referring to the

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criteria or stages suggested by Baron & Kenny (1986). The mediation effect analysis in this study was conducted to answer or prove the fifth hypothesis (H5). To determine whether customer satisfaction can mediate the influence of customer value on customer loyalty, as shown in Figure 3 below:

Figure 3 Test of the Mediation

Based on the results of the Calculation for the Sobel test: An interactive calculation tool for mediation tests for the mediation effect as shown in Figure 5.15 and Figure 5.16, it can be explained that the coefficients of path a ($p = 0.041$), path b ($p = 0.000$) and path c ($p = 0.000$) are significant, and path $c' = 0.097$ (not significant). From the results of this analysis, it can be concluded that customer satisfaction mediates perfectly (fully mediation) in the relationship between the influence of customer value on customer loyalty in cafes in Lhokseumawe City.

The Influence of Moderation Effect

A moderating variable is a variable that influences (strengthens or weakens) the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Moderating variables are also called secondary independent variables (Sugiyono, 2019). The nature or direction of the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables may be positive or negative depending on the moderating variable; therefore, moderating variables are also called contingency variables. In SEM, several methods can be used to assess the moderating effect. One method that can estimate the moderating effect in complex SEM is the Ping method. According to Ping (1995) in Ghozali (2013), a single indicator should be used as an indicator of a moderating latent variable. This single indicator is the multiplication of the exogenous latent variable indicator with the moderator variable indicator. For example, the relationship between X and Y is influenced by the latent variable Z, where Y is the dependent manifest variable, while X and Z are latent variables, each with its own indicator. The effect of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty, moderated by the cafe atmosphere, can be seen. This can be seen in Figure 4 below:

Figure 4 Moderating Effects of Cafe Atmosphere

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Based on the moderation effect model shown in Figure 4 above, the regression weight value of the moderating effect of cafe atmosphere on customer satisfaction towards cafe customer loyalty in Lhokseumawe City is explained in Table 4 below:

Table 7 Regression Values of Moderation Effect Model

			Std. Estimate	Unstd. Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Customer Loyalty	<---	Customer satisfaction	0,25	0,191	0,084	2,258	0,024
Customer Loyalty	<---	Cafe Atmosphere	0,391	0,31	0,086	3,588	***
Customer Loyalty	<---	Interaction	0,494	0,009	0,003	3,431	***

From Table 7 above, it can be concluded that the standardized regression weights for the direct influence of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty have a regression coefficient value of 0.25 and a significant value of 0.024 (≤ 0.05). Then, the cafe atmosphere has a direct effect on customer loyalty with a regression coefficient of 0.391 and a significance value of 0.000 (≤ 0.05). Furthermore, the interaction between customer satisfaction and cafe atmosphere also has a significant effect on customer loyalty with a regression coefficient value of 0.494 with a significance value of 0.000 (≤ 0.05). Thus, it can be said that the cafe atmosphere variable is an exogenous variable that directly affects customer loyalty, but also as a moderator variable that interacts with customer satisfaction and then affects cafe customer loyalty in Lhokseumawe City.

Discussion

Verification hypothesis testing can be performed by comparing probability values at significance levels of 1%, 5%, and 10%. For clarity, this will be explained as follows:

1. Statistical Hypothesis Formulation (H1): Customer value has a significant influence on customer satisfaction of cafes in Lhokseumawe City.

Based on Table 6, the analysis results using SEM AMOS obtained a critical value (CR) for the influence of the customer value variable on customer satisfaction of 2.049. This calculated t-value is above the t-table value of 1.98 and the probability value (significance) is 0.04 (smaller than the standard 0.05). Therefore, it can be concluded that customer value has a significant effect on customer satisfaction in cafes in Lhokseumawe City. This means that the first hypothesis (H1) proposed previously is accepted. The results of this study are in line with several previous studies, such as Blut et al., (2024) which states that good customer value can encourage increased customer satisfaction. The same thing was also conveyed by Widjaja & Araufi, (2020), which states that customer value is an important factor in increasing customer satisfaction. Further research, (Patil and Rane, 2023; Qiu et al., 2024; Saputra, 2018), finding customer value also has a significant influence on customer satisfaction, including emotional value (Rafdinal and Suhartanto, 2020). The study of the concept of value is seen as increasingly important amidst increasingly fierce competition in the cafe industry.

2. Statistical Hypothesis Formulation (H2): Customer value has a significant influence on cafe customer loyalty in Lhokseumawe City.

The analysis results obtained a critical value (CR) for the influence of the customer value variable on customer loyalty of 5.488. This calculated t-value is above the t-table value of 1.98 and the probability value (significance) is 0.000 (smaller than the standard of 0.05). Therefore, it can be concluded that customer value has a significant effect on customer loyalty in cafes in Lhokseumawe City. This means that the second hypothesis (H2) proposed previously is accepted. The results of this study are in line with Gabriella Santoso & Ruslim, (2024), which found that customer value has a significant influence on customer loyalty. And the study, Gallarza-granizo et al., (2019), also found that increasing customer value will have an impact on increasing customer loyalty. Another study also found that perceived value can increase customer satisfaction and loyalty (Jeong and Kim, 2019).

3. Statistical Hypothesis Formulation (H3): Customer satisfaction has a significant influence on cafe customer loyalty in Lhokseumawe City.

The results of the data analysis obtained a critical value (CR) identical to the calculated t-value for the influence of the customer satisfaction variable on customer loyalty of 3.554. This calculated t-value is above the t-table value of 1.98 and the probability value (significance) is 0.000 (smaller than the standard of 0.05). Therefore, it can be concluded that customer satisfaction has a significant effect on customer loyalty in cafes in Lhokseumawe City. This means that the second hypothesis (H3) proposed previously is accepted. The results of this study are in line with research (Karani et al., 2019), conducted research on several restaurants in Tangerang City and found that customer satisfaction significantly influences customer loyalty. Furthermore, several other studies in the food and beverage industry in more developed countries found that customer satisfaction is believed to be an important factor

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in increasing customer loyalty (Leroi-Werelds, 2019). The same thing was also conveyed by Gopi & Samat, (2020) that customer satisfaction has a significant influence on customer loyalty.

4. Statistical Hypothesis Formulation (H4): Cafe atmosphere has a significant influence on cafe customer loyalty in Lhokseumawe City.

Based on the results of data analysis, the critical value (CR) for the influence of the cafe atmosphere variable on customer loyalty was 3.588. This calculated t-value is above the t-table value of 1.98, and the probability value (significance) is 0.000 (smaller than the standard 0.05). Therefore, it can be concluded that cafe atmosphere has a significant effect on cafe customer loyalty in Lhokseumawe City. This means that the second hypothesis (H4) proposed previously is accepted. The results of this study are in line with research Rafli et al., (2024) at Meraki Café, Cirebon, and several other researchers, such as (Atsnawiyah et al., 2021; Mudjiyanti, 2022; Risal et al., 2025), shows that the cafe atmosphere can influence customer satisfaction and loyalty. A similar finding was also found by (Hidayati et al., 2024; Hikmah et al., 2023), which states that store atmosphere has a strong impact on consumers' decisions to revisit. This shows that atmosphere is not just an aesthetic element, but a strategic part of building long-term relationships with customers.

5. Statistical Hypothesis Formulation (H5): Customer value has a significant influence on cafe customer loyalty in Lhokseumawe City with customer satisfaction as a mediating variable.

Based on the results of the power analysis, it can be explained that the significance of path a consists of the relationship between customer value and customer satisfaction of 0.041, the significance of path b consists of the relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty of 0.000, and the significance of path c consists of the relationship between customer value and customer loyalty of 0.000. The significance of the three paths meets the theoretical criteria (Baron and Kenny, 1986). Furthermore, to assess the indirect influence relationship, the significance value of the c' path can be calculated using the Calculation for the Sobel test: An interactive calculation tool for mediation tests. The Sobel calculator calculation found a significance value of 0.097 (not significant). The results of the calculation of the mediation effect as shown in Figure 3 can be explained that the coefficients of path a, path b and path c are significant, and path c' is not significant, so it can be concluded that customer satisfaction plays a role as a perfect mediation (fully mediation), in the relationship between customer value and customer loyalty of cafes in Lhokseumawe City. The results of this study are in line with research (El-Adly, 2019; Guhl et al., 2019), who found that customer perceived value in hotel services has a significant indirect positive influence on customer loyalty, with customer satisfaction acting as a mediator. Then Cho et al., (2020) He stated that customer satisfaction is important for encouraging customer loyalty, which is previously derived from perceived value. Then, a study in the public sector found that customer satisfaction can mediate the relationship between perceived value and customer loyalty (Gabriella Santoso and Ruslim, 2024; Jeong and Kim, 2019).

6. Statistical Hypothesis Formulation (H6): Cafe atmosphere moderates the relationship between customer satisfaction and cafe customer loyalty in Lhokseumawe City.

The results of the data analysis obtained a critical value (CR) for the influence of the INTERAK variable on customer loyalty of 3.431. This calculated t-value is above the t-table value of 1.98 and the probability value (significance) of 0.000 (smaller than the standard of 0.05). So it can be concluded that the INTERAK variable of cafe atmosphere can moderate the relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. This means that the sixth hypothesis (H6) proposed previously is accepted. The type of moderation found is a quasi-moderator (pseudo-moderator). It is called a pseudo-moderator because the cafe atmosphere functions as an exogenous (independent) variable and simultaneously interacts with other independent variables (customer loyalty). Thus, it can be said that the cafe atmosphere variable is an exogenous (independent) variable that directly affects customer loyalty, but also as a moderator variable that interacts with customer satisfaction and then affects cafe customer loyalty in Lhokseumawe City.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that customer value has a significant influence on customer satisfaction, which in turn has a positive impact on customer loyalty in cafes in Lhokseumawe City. The higher the value perceived by customers, whether in terms of product quality, reasonable prices, or service, the higher their level of satisfaction. This satisfaction then drives loyalty, which is reflected in the tendency of customers to return, recommend the cafe to others, and have a long-term commitment to the cafe. The findings also indicate that cafe atmosphere, such as comfort, lighting, interior design, music, and cleanliness, strengthen the relationship between value and satisfaction, as well as between satisfaction and customer loyalty. In this context, cafe atmosphere is not merely a complement, but a crucial element in creating a pleasant and memorable experience for customers. Practically, the results of this

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study provide input for cafe owners and managers in Lhokseumawe to focus not only on product quality and price, but also pay more attention to creating a cafe atmosphere that supports comfort and social interaction. Theoretically, this research strengthens the customer value theory and the stimulus-organism-response concept, where the physical environment (atmosphere) acts as a stimulus capable of influencing customers' internal states (satisfaction) and generating behavioral responses in the form of loyalty. Furthermore, this research also opens up opportunities for further study on how specific elements of a cafe atmosphere can be optimized to enhance the customer experience in the service industry, particularly in a local context.

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